

DEVELOPING PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' ENGLISH COMMUNICATION SKILLS AND TEAM BUILDING THROUGH FAN-N-PICK LEARNING MODEL

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Abstract:

In 21st century education, there are four key skills that students need to acquire: communication, critical thinking, creativity and collaboration. The study aims to explore the application of Fan-n-Pick learning model and to improve English communication skills and team building through the application of Fan-n-Pick learning model. This study is a report on practice in the classroom. The subjects of the study were the Year Three students who are aged 9 of a selected primary school in Malaysia. The data collection instrument consists of the teachers' and students' observation sheet and the observation sheets of team building activities and reports. Data was analysed using qualitative method. The results of the study show that the application of Fan-N-Pick learning model for the primary school students is well-performed. Hence, the learning model can develop primary students' English communication skills and their team building.

Keywords: Fan-N-Pick learning model, English communication skills, team building, students

1. Introduction

According to Malaysia Education Blueprint 2013-2025, teaching and learning processes are being introduced to a new level as being the 21st century teaching and learning concept. The concept is focusing on student centered concept and teacher as the facilitator during the teaching and learning activity specifically to ensure the students can enhance their ability to work in group. Thus, the quality of education should be able to improve the achievement of learners so concerned is able to face and solve the problems that has been faced. To deal with these problems, it required the role of teachers must have wide knowledge about the media learning conditions of the students, and implement effective

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learning and meaningful (Hosnan, 2014). This means that teachers must have responsibility for the tasks to be carried out in accordance with the demands of their profession that is as professional educators. The vital task is the responsibility of a professional educator is able to stimulate, guide, direct and also encourage creativity in the learning development. Thus, all efforts must be developed in the learning of teachers in designing interesting learning. There is a need to collaborate between students and teachers in form of learning model that can motivate the students to learn and communicate in English effectively. There are some main issues that were identified for this study which is that the students are lack of English communication skills in order to converse well in English and they are also unable to work well in group. Improving the students' speaking ability in English is one of the most important challenges that the teachers try to achieve. In the previous lessons, it was found that the certain group members will take part and some other members had shown no interest at all. Usually, this scenario had occurred because only the good students will take over or control and do their tasks in their own way. They did not give any chance to other students to be involved, especially for the weaker students. Hereby, it was found that the teaching and learning process is not so successful, and the objective of the lesson is not fully achieved. Besides, almost all students could not understand the lesson on that day. Due to the reason of not optimal use of learning model that has been implemented by the teacher, it is a need to improve and provide a pleasant atmosphere in the process of teaching and learning in the classroom, it should be tried implementation of cooperative learning model. This model requires students to have social skills, thinking skills and be able to construct their own knowledge, can involve all students learn in the classroom, developing teams and communicating well either as individuals or groups. Learning model that will be done is Fan-n-Pick model. The Fan-n-Pick is a cooperative learning model developed by Kagan and Kagan (2009). It was chosen for this model because it involves the activity of all students so they can have social skills. The students are able to exchange and obtain information by communicating in English, and team building skills. With this cooperative learning, teaching and learning in the classroom is expected to affect the pattern of interaction of students. The model aims to improve the social and language skills and students' team work skills through team building activities which can enhance the activity and cooperation among students. Thus, the researchers want to increase students' English communication skills and team building skills by replacing conventional methods commonly used by social studies with the innovative teaching method which had not previously been employed by the school teachers. Hence, it is expected that this study can build the students' confident in communicating English, build their interest in English learning and enhance team building skills through group activities.

2. Literature Review

With the emergence of new technology, English has become a global language, and proficiency in English communication skills is considered highly essential for a person's personal and professional growth. Communication generally means the transfer of ideas, feelings, plans, messages, or information from one person to another.

2.1 Teacher's Role in Teaching Speaking Skills

English Communication skills are a crucial tool for global setting of the new millennium and this recognized by academicians and industry. English Communication skills are also important, given its widespread status across the globe as a lingua franca. Definitely, multilingual skills are considered a noticeable feature in the make-up of the new global engineer. English communication skills are important for a student who seeks to carry out his or her professional practice in the global arena. Speaking is crucial to effective communication and it is the purposeful process by which people using distinct and detectible symbols. Besides, it uses communicate meaning in the minds of their listeners. It is flexible, changing as well as complex and varied. It is one of the subjects where the students are expected to speak English in their daily communication. It is because English is a second language and an international language.

Brown (2001) argues that when someone can speak a language, it means that he can convey on a conversation rationally proficiently. The main goal of teaching speaking is communicative efficiency. Teaching speaking means helping learners develop their ability to interact successfully in the target language. To do so, one must have communicative competence. Thus, to help students to enhance their speaking skills, the teacher must help students improve their grammar, enrich their vocabulary and manage interactions in terms of who says what, to whom, when and about what. For teaching, a teacher needs to adopt such skills of communication which motivate the students toward their learning process according to students' ability (Sng Bee, 2012). The same type of speaking activity might be practiced several times during the skill acquisition process; however, the task requirements should be of increasing levels of difficulty. With students of differing abilities in many language classes are big, the teachers need to strive in helping students to improve their speaking skills. Thus, group work has proved to be an effective way to solve the problem as group work allows all students to practice language and to actively participate (Baker & Westrup, 2000). In addition, group work is highly recommended by many experts as a useful technique to get students involved in classroom activities, increase student talking time, and reduce teacher talking time (Brumfit, 1984; Harmer, 1991).

2.2 Fan-n-Pick Learning Model

Kagan & Kagan (2009), indicate the steps of cooperative learning model of Fan-n-Pick is i) student card holds the number one problem/question with a shape like a fan and say 'take a card', any card up; 2) the second student draws a card, read the questions aloud,

giving the about five seconds to think; 3) student number three answered questions; 4) student number four responded from the students answers number three, for right or wrong answer, the student number four proofread and give a perception or guidance to the students' answers number three,-for answers that do not have a right or wrong answer, the student number four does not check the truth, but to praise and then summarize the thinking of the answer; 5) students switch roles one goes according clockwise for each new round. According to Ana and Siti (2018), cooperative learning model is a learning model which includes the participation of groups. This model will help to increase student activity, improve reasoning, logical thinking, active, creative, open, and curious. The cooperative learning model of Fan n Pick and Pairs Compare can develop students' learning and motivation and students' learning output (Yudianto, Budi and Ludi, 2018), Rafidah et al. (2018) suggests that their innovative card game develop cooperative learning model and enhance English communication skill among students. Another study done by Frianto (2016) found that the cooperative learning model Team Game Tournament and Fan-N-Pick will increase the motivation and the quality of learning.

2.3 The Team Building Concept

A team is a group of people working towards a common goal. Boss (1983:66) defined teambuilding as *"interventions designed to improve effectiveness in working together by confronting and resolving problems"*. Team Building includes the process of enabling the group of people to reach their goals. It contains of steps like clarification of team goals; identification of hindrances to goal achievements; facing the identified challenges and enabling the achievement of the goals. According to Fajana (2002), teamwork is an integration of resources and inputs working in harmony to achieve organizational goals, where roles are prescribed for every organization member, challenges are equally faced and incremental improvements are sought continually. Katzenbach and Smith (1993) notes that a team can simply be defined as a small number of people, with a set of performance goals, who have a commitment to a common purpose and an approach for which they hold themselves mutually accountable. The suggestion here is that teams must be of a manageable size and that all team members must be committed to reach team goals. In addition, the team members must be jointly accountable for their actions and the outcomes of these actions. Team building has several major objectives one of which is enhancing good communications with participants as team members and individuals. It is also aimed at ensuring clear work objectives and a climate of cooperation and collaborative problem-solving.

3. Methodology

This study used a classroom action research method (CAR). According to Arikunto, et al. (2012) the class action research is an action that has been planned to the learning activities in a class presence. The roles of the researcher are as an action planner, action executive,

observer, interviewer, data collector, data analyzer, and author of research report. The model used in the process defines four steps and repetitions. This model has been developed by Kemmis and Taggart (1988) as illustrated in the following figure.

Figure 1: The Action Research Model (Kemmis & McTaggart, 1988:14)

In this study, the subject is the Year Three students of a selected primary school in Perak, Malaysia. 20 students consisting of 8 males and 12 females were involved in this study. Table 1 shows the details of the required data source of the study.

Table 1: Data and data Source of the Research

No	Variable	Instruments	Technique	Source
1	Fan-n Pick Learning Model	Observation sheet for the application of Fan-n-Pick Learning Model	Observation	Teacher and students
2	English Communication Skills	Observation sheet on students' English communication skills	Observation	Students
3	Team Building Activities	Observation sheet on students' team building activities	Observation	Students

For this study, the data were collected through observation sheets and reports. Data were analyzed by using flow models of descriptive qualitative analysis (Miles & Huberman, 1994). The data were analyzed and measured in the third stage to decide the outcome. If the desired outcome has not been reached, then the next process stage will be evaluated with changes and modifications. The next cycle is a continuation of the previous cycle and so the predicted outcomes are achieved.

4. Results and Discussion

In this study, the instrument used to test the practicality of Fan-n-Pick learning model is an observation sheet containing an observer evaluation. The instrument is based on feasibility study obtained from data. The findings can be indicated that the degree of

feasibility analysis by teachers and teachers in teaching has improved from cycle I to cycle II. The teacher's mean level in the learning activities increased from 78.86% with good criteria. The first cycle increased to 89.08% with the criteria very well in the second cycle. The learning activities by students, the average rate of 70.34 % on its suitability with good criteria for the first cycle to 85.65% with the criteria very well in the second cycle, there is an improvement in the implementation of teacher and student learning activities from the cycle I to cycle II.

In the first cycle to second cycle for the application Fan-n Pick learning model, the result showed that the students achieved better in their activities. The findings show that the students can communicate, exchange knowledge, co-operate, support each other. Besides that, they are able to have more confident to speak in English and converse well with their friends so that it can improve English communication skills and team building skills to enhance social relations, as well as character building of the students. Thus, this situation is supported with communicative language teaching approach (CLT) proposed by (Brown, 2007), a methodology that emphasizes authenticity, interaction, student-centered learning, task-based activities, and communication for the real world and meaningful purposes. This is what underlies that to achieve these activities, students must be guided to communicate with their peers. Interacting with the group members can not only encourage students to communicate effectively, but can also teach students to have the communication skills and not limit themselves to grammatical or linguistic skills. This learning allows students to use language techniques which designed to engage learners in the pragmatic, authentic and functional use of language for meaningful purposes. In this communicative classroom, students ultimately have to speak fluently and accurately and use the language productively and receptively in impromptu contexts.

Moreover, according to Kagan (2009), That the cooperative learning model Fan-n Pick is learning that has a systemic role to construct in the study group so that the interaction between group members influences each other to generate new ideas, to communicate information and its community, to carry out learning based on formal procedures and integrated into the lesson plan and to help students foster social interactions. Team building referred to the act of improving and maximizing a group of such people who collaborate or work together to achieve a common goal and also to enhance social relations and define roles within teams, often involving collaborative tasks.

The application of Fan-n-Pick learning model was adapted and innovated from the Kagan Cooperative Learning Strategy that helps to engage all students in the learning process. This activity requires the students to speak and communicate effectively with their peers in order to ensure the activity is carried out successfully. The implementation of Fan-n-Pick is done in the classroom consists of : 1) the teacher prepares the role card which one question is written on each card 2) the teacher distributes the role cards and asks students to choose a role 2) each team receives a set of 8 questions cards 3) the teacher distributes the role cards to every group and asks the students to pick a role ; Fanner,

Reader, Answerer and Praiser 4) the Fanner hold question cards in a fan and says "Pick a card" to the Reader 5) the Reader picks a card, reads the question out aloud and allow five seconds of think time to the Answerer 6) the Answerer answers the question 7) the Praiser paraphrases the answer that the Answerer gave 8) the group praises the Answerer 9) the students switch roles one person clockwise for each new round 10) the cards are then rotated one person to the right and the steps are repeated. Increased learning application by teachers and students is due to improvements already made by teachers at the time of execution of the second cycle of learning activities which become deficient in cycle I.

Evidently, Fan-n-Pick learning model includes all students. Students actively learn together and contributes ideas and they do not feel insecure about speaking English but speak with their friends more confidently. The students gave positive response to the type of Fan-n-Pick learning model. As well as being easy to communicate in English, students are enthusiastic and happy and can learn with a group. Group learning makes students happy because it got bored in the classroom, no students just sat there quietly and students help each other to figure out teacher questions. Students are also happy to collaborate with friends because the group can help each other and students pay more attention to friends, students can understand the material more easily through a role card and learn from it. Thus, it can be applied again at the next meeting. The instrument used for determining the English communication skills in the application of Fan-n-Pick learning model was the observation sheet. The measurement results of obtaining an average value of 77.06 with good criteria in the first process, while the second criterion very well achieve an average value of 86.78 with the criterion. The achievement meets the indicators of performance indicators.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the application of Fan-n-Pick learning model can develop Year Three students' English communication skills and their team building skills. During the teaching process, teachers act as facilitators and motivators and students in the group tried to converse in English more confident through group discussion activities. Students are able to deliver information well and use various vocabularies in English. They also carried out their duties with full responsibility during the activities. They helped each other to solve tasks given by their teacher and work together with their friends. They had a mutual cooperation in earnest, there is no longer a passive student in the classroom, each concerned with the group's problems and can be restrained in expressing opinions.

5. Conclusion

The application of Fan-n-Pick learning model for the Year Three students in this primary school is well-performed. Therefore, the few recommendations can be suggested based on these results. In the implementation of learning activities, teachers should do the proper planning of the learning model that will be used in learning. Teachers need to do the proper preparation of the curriculum model which will be used in curriculum while

conducting learning activities. Other teachers are suggested to implement cooperative learning Fan-n-Pick because it can improve students' English communication skills and team building skills. Nevertheless, it is proposed that the lecturers or teachers adapt this model according to the needs and context of the students.

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